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Abstract

This deliverable describes the communications strategy and plan for Month 13 to Month 24 of GN5-1.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the communications strategy and plan for Month 13 to Month 24 (M13–M24) of GN5-1.

Continuing from the progress made in Year 1 of GN5-1, the document provides the context on which the communications strategy and plan is built, and details the key communication aspects that were considered in devising the communications plan.

Actions identified in the plan will be tracked on an ongoing basis and their success measured against the key performance indicators set for the Communications Task. Progress towards objectives will be monitored and reported on a regular basis.

1 Introduction

Informed by the goals set for GN5-1 in the project's Description of Work (DoW), the marketing and communications strategy and plan continues to address the project's different stakeholders and their requirements, with integrated, consistent communications that aim to target audiences through coordinated channels, with consistent messaging and impactful content.

Following the strategic direction set for GN5-1, this document sets out the communications strategy Task 1 Communications and Design of Work Package 2 Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement (WP2 T1) has devised to progress and enhance the work it started in GN4-3 and continued in Year 1 of GN5-1 (Section 2).

The communications plan the Task has compiled is based on the communications strategy, and key communication aspects as well as stakeholder impact were considered in putting the plan together (Section 3).

To track progress against the communications plan, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been agreed, which the Task will monitor on a regular basis (Section 4).

The document concludes by summarising the key approaches required for the Task to succeed in meeting its objectives and how it hopes to further progress its efforts (Section 5).

This deliverable is based on and updates the marketing and communications strategy and plan for Months 1 to 12 of the GN5-1 project [[GN5-1 D2.1](#)].

2 Project Communications Strategy

The GN5-1 Description of Work includes the following overarching objective:

GN5-1 aims to address the challenge to provide faster, resilient, agile and secure connectivity and collaboration services for an increasing amount of data, to enable scientists, researchers and students access to near-real-time applications that support evidence-based decision-making in society, and worldwide effective collaboration of virtual research communities.

Specific objectives relevant to project communications include:

- O2. To understand and serve the communication networking needs and collaboration between the European NRENs, their expanding user community and important European and global stakeholder groups.*
- O4. To facilitate and enable, through the project, the needs of a wide user base across multiple disciplines for excellent science and research by delivering a broad range of existing and innovative new services. These services incorporate agile incubator development and sustainable operation following thorough business model practices.*

Informed by the above, the marketing communications strategy aims to raise awareness of the project, its activities and ambitions, as well as the network and services, and highlight the impact these have on the research and education community. This should be done through identification of stakeholders, defining attributes of those stakeholders (or “personas”), composing clear messaging and positioning statements, the production and publication of engaging content to address key stakeholders, and communication delivery through integrated, measurable and collaborative channels.

WP2’s communications, marketing and events service has continued to develop and evolve over the years and has proved itself to be an effective and valuable resource. It is also responsible for building and maintaining the GÉANT name, brand and reputation. In GN5-1 this is added to with a Task focused on policy engagement (WP2 T4), which will ensure closer coordination on outreach and messaging relevant to specific stakeholders that are associated with the activities of that Task.

Over successive GÉANT projects, the WP2 team has established and developed effective communication channels which maximise the reach of the messages and content to a wide range of GÉANT stakeholder communities. Examples include the range of GÉANT websites as part of the renewed web presence completed under GN4-3; the CONNECT family of channels (website, newsletter and magazine); participation at events; joint promotional campaigns with National Research and Education Networks (NRENs); and a social media approach that targets all stakeholders and drives traffic to GÉANT websites. Furthermore, the TNC event organised by GÉANT and partner NRENs routinely attracts over 800 attendees, offers an online platform that attracts several hundred further attendees, and reaches an audience of several thousand watching streamed content online.

In GN5-1 WP2 will aim to increase the effectiveness of these channels and determine how well messaging is reaching its intended audience, by monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs), liaising with partners, reporting on campaigns, and adjusting activity where needed.

WP2 will continue to establish, maintain, and develop relationships and collaborate with other groups to support outreach efforts, making joint use of channels and opportunities to reach audiences. This may include the Special

Interest Group on Marketing Communications (SIG-Marcomms), the In the Field blog, the Science|Business weekly newsletter, stakeholder joint collaborations, EC websites, featured opportunities and social media, and, of course, the partners' own dissemination of information across all their channels. WP2 will continue to use the most appropriate tools to monitor/measure the impact of the communications to ensure they are relevant, targeted, and cost-effective.

WP2 will continue to support WP1 Project Management and its Tasks with internal communications efforts and to support recruitment, retention and ongoing training of project staff.

WP2 works closely with the other Work Packages, in particular with WP3 User and Stakeholder Engagement, to develop and implement communications plans that will enable dissemination and promotion, as well as allow dialogue with and feedback from the stakeholder groups.

To continue the progress achieved in GN4-3 and in Months 1 to 12 of GN5-1, Task 1 has identified a number of objectives and actions for M13–M24. These will be accomplished by building on the “twin track” approach employed to date, an approach that separates “features” (functional) and “benefits” (impactful) to address different stakeholders with the most appropriate and compelling content and deliver this through targeted channels.

The Task will continue to work closely with the other Work Packages, with project partners and participants, and with other stakeholders to ensure the widest reach.

As an integral part of its work, each Work Package of GN5-1 will disseminate its results to relevant audiences, in coordination with the support WPs (WP1, WP2, WP3). This will include:

- Presentations.
- Training and knowledge-sharing at meetings and conferences.
- Issuing news stories, use studies and service documentation.
- E-infrastructure integration projects and suppliers through operational collaborations with, for example, international networking organisations.

A core role of WP2 Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement is to disseminate and promote the results and outputs of the project across the stakeholder communities through external and internal communications strategies and actions, helping to increase the success and adoption of services. To ensure partner involvement, this work is carried out in collaboration with WP3 User and Stakeholder Engagement.

The project communications strategy informs the communications plan, which is detailed in the next section.

3 Project Communications Plan

Focusing on a set of objectives (see Section 3.2) that have been informed by the strategy outlined in Section 2, the communications plan defines the information dissemination required to meet these objectives by answering the following questions:

- What type of information needs to be disseminated?
- Which communication channels should be used?
- Who does it need to be delivered to and what are their characteristics?
- When should it be delivered?
- How can it best be measured?

The success of actions is measured against key performance indicators (KPIs).

This section discusses the key communication aspects that have been taken into account to produce the communications plan, as well as presenting the plan itself.

3.1 Strategic Considerations

In putting together the marketing communications plan, Task 1 has followed the devised strategy by considering key communication aspects. These are the audiences that need to be addressed, which channels are appropriate for addressing the different audiences, what messaging approach will deliver the best results, how content is conveyed most effectively, and how stakeholder engagement can be ensured. Each of these is discussed below.

3.1.1 Audiences

The GÉANT project has a diverse range of audiences (many of whom are stakeholders, see Section 3.1.5.1), including:

- a. Work Package Leaders (WPLs), Task Leaders (TLs), Coordinators and project participants.
- b. Project partners (European NRENs) and the research and education institutions they serve.
- c. E-infrastructure partners and other organisations in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem.
- d. Research communities.
- e. The European Commission.
- f. National governments.
- g. Global partners – non-European NRENs, Regional Research and Education Networks (RRENs).
- h. Industry – potential and existing suppliers, sponsors, etc.
- i. The public.

These audiences have different interests, different requirements for information and levels of engagement, and will often get their information from different communication channels.

3.1.2 Channels

Reaching the project audiences requires a range of communication channels that cater for different types of content and consumption. The project therefore uses different channels for different purposes. Channels employed include:

Web presences, e.g.

1. GEANT.org
2. CONNECT.geant.org
3. IMPACT.geant.org
4. NETWORK.geant.org
5. COMMUNITY.geant.org
6. ABOUT.geant.org
7. RESOURCES.geant.org
8. CAREERS.geant.org

Weekly newsletters:

9. GÉANT Project Office news from the Project Management Office (PMO) for project participants.
10. CONNECT weekly newsletter subscribed to by a wide range of audiences.

Quarterly newsletters:

11. Newsletter distributed to key EC personnel with selected content from *CONNECT* magazine (published in March, June and October).

Magazine:

12. *CONNECT* magazine.

Other:

13. Social media to raise awareness, engage with audiences, and drive traffic to web presences:
 - LinkedIn.
 - Facebook.
 - X (formerly known as Twitter).
 - Mastodon.
 - YouTube.
 - Instagram.
14. Internal meetings (e.g. Project Management Convention and Symposium; certain SIGs – SIG-Marcomms and SIG-MSP).
15. External events (such as TNC).

Throughout GN4-3 and Year 1 of GN5-1 significant progress was made in improving the project's communication channels, particularly ensuring they were fully accessible, optimised for mobile devices, designed to provide a consistent brand identity and user experience, and worked well together. Indeed, GÉANT's web presence was transformed, replacing a single site of over 700 pages with multiple new "lighter" sites built on a common WordPress platform, joined with a single navigation, and including a global search function allowing content across all sites to be searched from any single site. These lighter sites address key areas and stakeholders with

tailored content, and the common platform means content published on the CONNECT website can be easily and quickly propagated across relevant subject-specific sites.

Table 3.1 below summarises the audiences and approach for each channel.

#	Channel	Audiences	Approach
1.	GEANT.org	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	As the default entry point for all GÉANT audiences, this site aims to provide a brief overview of all activities with high-level messaging – for a potentially diverse group of audiences. From here, visitors are directed to the subject-specific sites for further information.
2.	CONNECT.geant.org	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h	As the home of all timely content – news and articles about all topics and event notifications – for use by the project and its partners, this channel caters for a diverse audience.
3.	IMPACT.geant.org	b, c, d, e, f, g, i	This site is intended primarily for audiences who know little about GÉANT or its services, and as such content is written in non-technical language to highlight the socio-economic impact of the project.
4.	NETWORK.geant.org	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	This site is for a potentially diverse group of audiences and aims to showcase the pan-European network and to provide a platform on which to disseminate and promote the GN4-3N project activities and achievements.
5.	COMMUNITY.geant.org	a, b, c, d, e, g, h, i	This site is to showcase the GÉANT Community Programme, promote involvement with Task Forces (TFs), SIGs and workshops, and to facilitate voting in the Community Award. It also provides an overview of the Learning and Development opportunities.
6.	ABOUT.geant.org	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	This site provides background information about GÉANT – the Association primarily – and therefore includes information on the membership and project partners, GÉANT Board, Executive Team, and offices. However, it also includes a resources section where white papers, position papers and strategy documents are published.
7.	RESOURCES.geant.org	a, b, e, g	This site provides a home for project output (deliverables, highlights) and more generic items such as logos, branding guidelines, etc.
8.	CAREERS.geant.org	a, b, i	This site is to support recruitment and retention of project staff. It aims to highlight the benefits of working for GÉANT and showcase successful employee journeys for interns, software engineers, network engineers, etc.
9.	PMO newsletter	a, e	This is targeted at all project participants and the EC Project Officer.

#	Channel	Audiences	Approach
10.	CONNECT newsletter	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	By incorporating content from the CONNECT.geant.org site it can be assumed that the newsletter audience is the same as the website. However, the audience can be analysed closely by the subscriber details.
11.	EC newsletter	e	The EC newsletter is new in GN5-1 and is compiled in collaboration with WP2 T4. It is targeted directly at EC staff and aims to raise awareness of those activities that are relevant to policy engagement.
12.	CONNECT magazine	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	The magazine is compiled and written so as to appeal to all audiences, with a tone and language that addresses different groups individually.
13.	Social media	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	By its very nature social media potentially covers all audiences. However, we are able to target particular audiences where appropriate.
14.	Internal meetings	a, b, e	Project-internal meetings include the Project Management Convention and Symposium, but also certain Special Interest Group (SIG) meetings, such as SIG-Marcomms and SIG-MSP. Whilst SIG meetings can include commercial partners, the delivery format for these meetings is aimed at project partners, who form the majority of attendees.
15.	External events	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	External events will vary in their audience focus and need to be addressed individually. For example, TNC is focused on European and non-European NRENs, RRENs, EC, and industry. However, ICT will focus on research communities, EC, national governments, industry and to a smaller extent the public.

Table 3.1: Communication channels – audiences and approach

3.1.3 Design

The design element of the Task is integral to all WP2 work, providing graphic design, video and animation creation/editing, website building, etc. to establish, maintain and ensure the consistency of brand identity. In Year 2, this work will include dedicated support for TNC24, including promotional materials such as animations, graphics, and campaign support; preparation for TNC25, including branding guidelines, website design, and promotion; service materials as driven by WP2 Task 2 plans – for example the redesign of eduroam and eduGAIN websites and the refresh of the eduMEET website; and ongoing development of channels such as the CONNECT, IMPACT, COMMUNITY, and NETWORK websites.

3.1.4 Messaging

A consistent and integrated approach to messaging helps to ensure the project and its activities are positioned correctly and seen as supporting wider initiatives, as well as building trust with stakeholders. The Task will continue to work with the Project Management Office (PMO) and with Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders (specifically WP2 Task 4 Policy Engagement) to develop project-wide messaging.

3.1.4.1 Key Areas

From a communications perspective, throughout GN4-3 and Year 1 of GN5-1 the project's wide range of activities were grouped into a number of key areas (networking, trust and identity, cloud services, community, and research engagement) to simplify project messaging and provide context to individual activities.

In particular, the areas of networking, trust and identity, and cloud services are central to Open Science and messaging will continue to support the high-level GÉANT objectives and positioning of the project within the Open Science landscape.

The community area covers such initiatives as TNC, the Task Forces and Special Interest Groups that foster innovation, the Community Award, and the Learning and Development work. The Task will continue to work closely with the GÉANT Community Programme to ensure communications efforts are aligned and supportive.

The research engagement area highlights the socio-economic impact of GÉANT and the NRENs on research, education, and the e-infrastructure communities – supporting the outreach efforts of Work Package 3 User and Stakeholder Engagement.

Year 2 of GN5-1 will continue to reflect this with a comprehensive web presence that sees each key area with its own website (e.g. network; community; impact) under a common navigation, supported by outreach efforts via social media and the newsletters, which both drive traffic to these websites and function as communication channels in their own right.

3.1.4.2 Twin Track Approach

Throughout GN4-3 and Year 1 of GN5-1 a “twin track” approach was followed with regard to messaging, which addresses communications through two main streams, impactful and functional. All the project's audiences, channels and content are included in these two groups.

- **Impactful:** a storytelling approach that addresses the “WHY?”, with engaging content highlighting the benefits. This may take the form of success stories, articles, videos, graphics, animations, social media campaigns such as Women in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Cyber

Security Month, posters and others, delivered through channels such as *CONNECT* magazine, the *CONNECT* website or the *IMPACT* website. For example, governments and funding bodies can read interviews or articles in *CONNECT* magazine, or success stories on the *IMPACT* website, which show the importance of the GÉANT community working with a particular research community, or how eduroam is supporting students across the world.

- **Functional:** an informational approach that addresses the “WHAT?”, highlighting the facts, features and necessary information. For example, service implementers in NRENs receive information on a particular service through internal meetings or via the WP3 Partner Relations Task or published on the GEANT.org website in appropriate sections. The information will focus on the features and technology of the service.

The twin track approach will be continued in Year 2.

Figure 3.1: Twin-track approach to messaging

3.1.5 Stakeholder Engagement

The Task will engage with all stakeholders, including Work Package Leaders and their Task Leaders, project partners and participants, the European Commission, and other partners.

Ongoing engagement with stakeholders, through both established and new channels, will be essential to the achievement of objectives. The level of detail will also be modified in accordance with the reader.

3.1.5.1 Stakeholder Impact Analysis

Table 3.2 lists the stakeholders of the GÉANT project and their interests, with the aim to determine the impact they have on marketing communications. This integrated approach to understanding the stakeholders is useful to ensure effective communications.

Stakeholders	Interests	Estimated Impact	Estimated Priority
WPLs/TLs	WPLs and TLs have a responsibility to disseminate their work and to engage with their audiences. The Task will work closely with them to ensure their communications needs are fully met and support the project's overall objectives.	Medium	2
Project participants (partners)	The way in which this stakeholder group consumes content is notable, as participants are often not involved in the project in a full-time capacity, and so the Task needs to compete for their attention and ensure the content is easy for them to consume.	Medium	2
EC	The EC requires the project to communicate its work and benefits to a wide range of audiences and needs to be kept up to date with developments and success stories. Therefore, the Task will work with the Project Officer to support their outreach efforts.	High	1
Other collaborators	The project needs to collaborate with a range of partners, and to support their outreach efforts, e.g., e-infrastructure partners and global partners. The Task will work with the relevant WPL/TL to ensure these collaborations continue to progress.	Medium	2

Table 3.2: Stakeholder impact analysis

3.2 Communications Plan

Taking into consideration all the factors discussed in Section 3.1, the communications plan (Table 3.3) details each objective, the actions to be taken to achieve it, the audiences targeted by the actions, the channels used to reach the audiences and how often the actions are to be executed.

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
Position and promote the GÉANT network and services to European and global (i.e. from world regions other than Europe) stakeholders.	Whilst necessary to promote the network and services to stakeholders, it is also important to support GÉANT's wider positioning within strategically important areas such as EuroHPC, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Digital Twin, etc.	Articulate and illustrate GÉANT's role in supporting initiatives such as EuroHPC and Digital Twin, via feature articles, web content, and graphics.	b, c, d, e, f, g, i	Feature articles and interviews with GÉANT Exec, Board members, and key members of the community, published in <i>CONNECT</i> magazine, relevant websites, and promoted on social media.	Quarterly
		Promote the next-generation network delivered by GN4-3N (which was fully rolled out at the end of GN5-1 Year 1) with ongoing articles, interviews, graphics, animations, etc. The completion of the network will be	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NETWORK website. • Social media. • CONNECT (all). • EC newsletter. 	Quarterly

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		marked by high-level announcements aimed at a wide range of target audiences through multiple channels.			
		Promote the achievements for each project period using content from the “Highlights” 2-page PDF created for EC reviewers.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GÉANT website. • Social media. • EC newsletter. • CONNECT magazine and newsletter. 	Annual
Demonstrate the capabilities, value, and impact of GÉANT, R&E networks, NREN partners and their portfolio of services.	It is essential to articulate and illustrate the GÉANT community’s socio-economic impact, not only supporting the ongoing funding efforts of project partners but highlighting the benefits of GÉANT	<p>Develop and grow the IMPACT.geant.org website, adding new stories and promoting these across GÉANT’s web presences and social media channels, and via NREN partners.</p> <p>The stories should reflect areas of importance for R&E and support the EC’s</p>	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IMPACT website. • Social media. • EC newsletter. • CONNECT magazine and newsletter. • CAREERS website. 	Quarterly

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
	to user communities.	<p>initiatives, and may be case studies or use cases as appropriate.</p> <p>A new section titled “By Nature Invisible” was added in M12. In Year 2 it will be further developed and new use cases with more service-related content will be added.</p> <p>A new section on SDGs should be added to showcase the work across the community in realising the achievement of individual SDGs.</p>			
<p>Showcase innovations and initiatives as well as user success stories and their impact.</p>	<p>The GÉANT Innovation Programme drives grass-roots innovation within the community and is an</p>	<p>Support outreach for the GÉANT Innovation Programme, helping to attract submissions for the funding process and</p>	<p>a, b, c, d, e</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COMMUNITY website. • CONNECT (all). 	<p>Quarterly</p>

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
	established part of the GÉANT Community Programme (GCP).	showcasing successful awardees and their work.			
Foster inclusion and participation among participants, partners, and the wider community.	Many project participants spend only a proportion of their time on the project; therefore, there is a need to engage, inform, and motivate participants through coordinated outreach and communications efforts, together with other Work Packages.	Support WP1 with PMO weekly newsletter to project participants; promote CONNECT weekly newsletter to grow participant subscribers.	a, b	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PMO weekly newsletter 	Weekly
		Support outreach efforts to attract, recruit, and retain project participant staff – including creation of “Life at GÉANT” articles (not restricted to Association staff only); development and updating of CAREERS.geant.org website; promoting vacancies on social media; promoting GÉANT Learning and	a, b, c, d, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media CAREERS website CONNECT (all) 	Monthly

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		Development (GLAD) material and courses; etc.			
		Where needed, update branding guidelines and presentation templates for all partners and participants to use, to ensure consistent branding and practice by project participants.	a, b, g	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RESOURCES website 	Quarterly
Collaborate with other e-infrastructure providers, users, NRENs in Europe and worldwide, commercial partners and other stakeholders to maximise dissemination reach.	GÉANT has a comprehensive range of channels. However, leveraging the reach of other stakeholders is important to maximise dissemination. Equally, it is important to support the outreach efforts of	Engage with NRENs and other stakeholders to collaborate on dissemination efforts, joint campaigns, and other initiatives. Utilise SIG-Marcomms meetings and mailing lists to identify potential collaborative campaigns; and	b, c, d, e, g, h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIG-Marcomms CONNECT Social media 	Ongoing

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
	others within the community.	contribute to best practice sessions at SIG-Marcomms meetings.			
	In particular, campaigns such as Women for STEM and Cyber Security Month actively involve project partners who submit articles and promote content through their own channels as part of a coordinated approach.	Collaborate with EC channels and publications such as Science Business to maximise reach of dissemination efforts.	b, c, d, e, f, g, h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E.g., Science Business, EC website, etc. – as needed. 	Ongoing
		Contribute articles and success stories to the EC for publishing through their channels.	b, c, d, e, f, g, h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EC websites and newsletters 	Ongoing
		Contribute to In the Field Stories and promote this initiative throughout GÉANT channels.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the Field site 	Monthly
		Invite contributed articles from NRENs and other partners for publishing in CONNECT channels.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CONNECT (all) 	Ongoing

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		Undertake joint press releases with suppliers where appropriate. Collaborate on joint announcements with user communities, NREs and RREs as required.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GÉANT website • CONNECT (all) • Other as needed 	As needed
Manage external communications channels and improve effectiveness of communications.	GÉANT communications channels must work together in an integrated way to ensure optimal user experience and to maximise effectiveness.	Continue to curate all websites and make ongoing improvements for user experience and impact.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i		Ongoing
		Collaborate regularly with WP3 to evolve <i>CONNECT</i> magazine to highlight GÉANT's role in strategically important topics; grow <i>CONNECT</i> weekly newsletter subscriber base; evolve <i>CONNECT</i> website for	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CONNECT (all) 	Ongoing

Objective	Additional Information	Action	Target Audiences	Channels	Frequency
		improved user experience.			
		Review use of social media and identify most appropriate platforms to use for particular content.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media 	Ongoing
Deliver a range of promotional materials to support outreach.		Produce project achievements sheets, slides with key highlights, ongoing web pages and banners for the GÉANT website.	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As needed. • RESOURCES website. 	Ongoing

Table 3.3: Communications plan

The identified actions will be tracked on an ongoing basis and their success measured against the KPIs set for the Task (see Section 4). Progress will be reported in quarterly management reports and any issues identified for monthly red, amber, green (RAG) status reports.

4 Key Performance Indicators

The success of the communications plan is measured against key performance indicators (KPIs).

The following KPIs have been set to support the monitoring of its effectiveness (baseline figures for 2023, i.e. M1–M12 of GN5-1, included):

- Social media: increase impressions (as an average across primary platforms – Facebook, X (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn)¹ by 10% per year.
 - 2023:
 - Facebook: 149,611 impressions, which equals a 9.6% increase.
 - X: 321,900 impressions, a 9.5% decrease.
 - LinkedIn: 291,100 impressions, a 51% increase.

On average, the impressions across the platforms increased by 17%, therefore the KPI in M1–M12 was achieved.
- Social media: increase total followers (as an average across primary platforms) by 8% per year.
 - End of 2023:
 - Facebook: 1,749, which equals an 18% increase.
 - X: 5,250, an 8.6% increase.
 - LinkedIn: 8,456, a 20.6% increase.

On average, the total followers across the platforms have increased by 16%, therefore the KPI in M1–M12 was achieved.
- Social media: achieve an engagement rate (as an average across primary platforms) of 2% per year.
 - 2023:
 - Facebook: 4.4%.
 - X: 4.3%.
 - LinkedIn: 5.3%.

On average, the engagement rate has increased by 4.67%, therefore the KPI in M1–M12 was achieved.
- Websites:^{2,3} increase total visitors to GEANT.org by 5% per year.
 - 2023: a 31.9% decrease. The reduction in the number of visitors is partly explained by the restructuring of GÉANT’s web presence, in which a single site of over 700 pages was replaced with multiple lighter sites. Nevertheless, as the default entry point for all GÉANT audiences, with the aim

¹ Mastodon currently does not collect/track data; gathering reliable consistent data from Instagram remains a challenge; and for YouTube we aim to track the most comparable data which is impressions click-through (2.6% in 2023).

² During the summer of 2023, Google officially retired Universal Analytics (UA), replacing it with the new Google Analytics 4 (GA4). Consequently, all analytics properties on GÉANT websites were updated to the new GA4 properties. It is important to note, however, that due to stricter policies, different tracking methods and setup, the data collected via GA4 properties is not entirely comparable with the data previously collected via the legacy UA. Significant discrepancies can be observed, especially in relation to users/visits, which are recorded according to different parameters on the two analytics services. As such, the values reported on the number of total visitors might not reflect the actual situation.

³ SECURITY.geant.org is not included because it does not allow tracking.

of providing a brief overview of all activities and high-level messaging, the GÉANT website remains an important channel and will be given focus in M13–M24 to ensure that the KPI is met (see Section 3.2).

- Websites: increase total visitors to IMPACT.geant.org by 5% per year.
 - 2023: a 56.3% decrease. Steps are already being taken to develop and grow the IMPACT.geant.org website (see Section 3.2) to ensure that the KPI will be met in M13–M24.
- Websites: increase total visitors to NETWORK.geant.org by 5% per year.
 - 2023: a 46.2% increase, therefore the KPI in M1–M12 was achieved.
- Websites: increase total visitors to CONNECT.geant.org by 10% per year.
 - 2023: a 53.7% increase, therefore the KPI in M1–M12 was achieved.

5 Conclusions

WP2 Task 1 Communications and Design has a broad remit, and it is anticipated that the objectives and associated actions identified in this deliverable will bring clarity and purpose to this, thus providing the best possible support to the project's objectives.

Certain approaches are required to ensure success:

- Close collaboration with Task 2 Services Marketing, Task 3 Events and Task 4 Policy Engagement within WP2, and with all Work Packages, particularly with WP3 User and Stakeholder Engagement.
- Ongoing and timely creation of engaging and appropriate content for diverse stakeholders, that can also be easily shared with and by project partners. The established "twin track" approach that has proved effective in GN4-3 and in Year 1 of GN5-1 will continue to be followed, as will the approach of recognising the need for a diverse range of content to suit the digital landscape, and subsequent evolving behaviours of audiences.

Having established and evolved the project's communications channels in GN4-3 and further in Year 1 of GN5-1, including the CONNECT family (magazine, website and newsletter) and the new web presences, it is envisaged that ongoing development will see an improvement in the effective use of the channels and more targeted dissemination.

Content creation that underpins GÉANT's strategic role is considered essential in the successful positioning of the project for future activities. The Task will therefore focus attention on topic areas such as EuroHPC, QKD, the UN's SDGs, and Destination Earth.

Campaigns to raise awareness of important topics, such as Women in STEM (both technical and non-technical support roles) and Cyber Security, will continue to be prominent in the communications mix. These campaigns engage project partners and other entities and can lead to significantly increased website traffic and social media engagement.

Increased support is anticipated for the recruitment and retention of project staff and communications has a role to play here. The development of the CAREERS.geant.org website and associated content to articulate and disseminate the benefits of working for GÉANT – including learning and development opportunities, internships, etc. – will be prioritised. Efforts will also be extended to highlight the role of project staff at partner organisations.

Progress towards these objectives will be monitored on a monthly basis, reported on at the Project Management Board meetings, and adjustments made where necessary to ensure completion.

References

[GN5-1_D2.1] https://resources.geant.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/GN5-1_D2-1_Project-Communications-Strategy-and-Plan.pdf

Glossary

DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EuroHPC	European High-Performance Computing
GA4	Google Analytics 4
GCP	GÉANT Community Programme
GLAD	GÉANT Learning and Development
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Project month
NREN	National Research and Education Network
O	Objective
PMO	Project Management Office
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
RAG	Red, Amber, Green – traffic-light colours used in project management to indicate status
RREN	Regional Research and Education Network
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIG	Special Interest Group
SIG-Marcomms	Special Interest Group on Marketing Communications
SIG-MSP	Special Interest Group on Management of Service Portfolios
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
T	Task
TF	Task Force
TL	Task Leader
TNC	The Networking Conference (formerly TERENA Networking Conference)
UA	Universal Analytics
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package
WP1	GN5-1 Work Package 1 Project Management
WP2	GN5-1 Work Package 2 Marcomms, Events and Policy Engagement
WP2 T1	WP2 Task 1 Communications and Design
WP2 T2	WP2 Task 2 Services Marketing
WP2 T3	WP2 Task 3 Events
WP2 T4	WP2 Task 4 Policy Engagement
WP3	GN5-1 Work Package 3 User and Stakeholder Engagement
WPL	Work Package Leader